

Quantitative Solubility Method for Studying Reversible One: One Complex Formation in Non-ideal Solutions

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Here is reported a solubility method for studying one: one charge transfer complex formation in non-ideal solutions. Formation constants and the heats of formation for the system nitrobenzene and some aromatic hydrocarbon donors have been calculated using this method. The values calculated for iodine-benzene and iodine-ether from the solubility data are in good agreement with spectrophotometric values. The results indicate that weak charge transfer complexes are formed because of specific interaction between individual hydrocarbon donor and nitrobenzene molecules.

Comprehensive work done on spectrophotometric studies of complex formation of reversible weak donor-acceptor complexes has not obscured Scott's¹ criticism of the validity of these methods. The usefulness of a comparison of thermodynamic constants, determined by spectrophotometric and non-spectrophotometric methods has been suggested^{2,3} in order to settle the questions of concerning the specifications of these weak interactions.

Andrews⁴ has reviewed non-spectrophotometric methods which can be used to study weak complexes. Out of the various methods reported in the literature, Hartley and Skinner's⁵ "Heat of solution method" has yielded some data for comparison with spectrophotometric data⁶. In an earlier work⁷, the determination of formation constant was not attempted on account of the unavailability of the various interaction parameters. The cryoscopic^{8,9} and the solubility¹⁰ method seem to be the only potential methods to yield sufficient data for comparison.

In the present investigation, the results of the studies of interaction between aromatic hydrocarbons and nitrobenzene using solubility method, are reported. The formation constants and the heats of formation have also been calculated. The agreement between equilibrium constants of iodine-benzene and iodine-ether determined by solubility, spectrophotometric and cryoscopic methods have been shown. The good agreement indicates that solubility method can yield valuable information about weak charge transfer complexes.

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EXPERIMENTAL

(i) *Chemicals*—All the chemicals used were obtained from B.D.H. Hydrocarbons were purified by crystallisation and sublimation. Nitrobenzene was dried and then twice distilled.

(ii) *Solubility Measurements*:—The solubilities were determined by synthetic method¹¹.

This method consisted in observing the solution temperature of the systems of known composition. The soda glass ampule containing known amounts of solute and solvent was sealed. It was then heated to dissolve all the solid and then cooled quickly by immersing in a freezing mixture of dry ice and acetone. On account of sudden cooling, the solid was precipitated in the form of fine crystals. The ampule was again warmed slowly in a water bath and the temperature at which last crystal dissolved was noted. A mean of several freezing and melting temperatures gave the solution temperature. The maximum error in the solution temperature is estimated as 0.1°. The rate of increase of temperature was maintained at less than 0.4° per minute. The plots of $\log x$ (solubility) versus $\frac{1}{T}$ were found to be straight line. The solubilities at the required temperatures (25° and 35°) were estimated from these plots. The results obtained are recorded in the following tables.

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

The results of solubility measurements are recorded in table I.

TABLE I

Solution temperature and mole fractions of the hydrocarbon in nitrobenzene.

Naphthalene		Phenanthrene		Anthracene		Biphenyl	
Solution Temperature °C	Mole Fraction						
14.8	0.2233	17.0	0.2119	19.0	0.00688	8.2	0.2142
19.8	0.2583	18.8	0.2217	16.6	0.00916	18.2	0.3012
24.8	0.2956	22.8	0.2512	23.0	0.01104	22.8	0.3414
27.0	0.2936	25.0	0.2570	25.0	0.01152	25.2	0.3601
28.8	0.3277	28.4	0.2801	34.3	0.01545	29.0	0.3944
29.4	0.3355	29.6	0.2892	35.0	0.01614	31.8	0.4192
35.0	0.3776	35.1	0.3204	39.8	0.01892	38.0	0.4907

TABLE II

Critical data

Component	Molar Value c.c	H _f Cals.	T _m	δ	Ideal solubility at 25°	Ideal solubility at 35°
Nitrobenzene	103	—	—	11.99	—	—
Benzene	89	—	—	9.15	—	—
Ether	105	—	—	7.4	—	—
Iodine	59	3740	386	14.1	0.1141 at 0°C	0.1418 at 16-6°C
Naphthalene	123	4440	352.9	10.07	0.3114	0.3973
Phenanthrene	156	6325	373.5	9.9	0.1155	0.1639
Anthracene	150	6888	490.0	9.8	0.01047	0.01531
Biphenyl	130.7	4004	343.0	10.0	0.4119	0.5190

TABLE III

Formation Constants and the Heats of Formation

Systems	Measured solubility at		Calculated solubility at		K at		ΔH in K cal.
	25°C	35°C	25°C	35°C	25°C	35°C	
Nitrobenzene-	0.2937	0.9776	0.2166	0.3036	0.5658	0.4444	5.35
Naphthalene							
Nitrobenzene-	0.2570	0.9200	0.0464	0.0742	8.5260	7.690	4.69
Phenanthrene							
Nitrobenzene-	0.0115	0.0161	0.0032	0.0049	2.666	2.357	2.42
Anthracene							
Nitrobenzene-	0.3590	0.4520	0.3078	0.4198	0.2821	0.1487	7.96
Biphenyl							
Ether iodine	*0.1320	*0.1442	0.00086	0.0014	20.58	14.10	3.18
Benzene-	at 0°C	at 16.6°C	at 0°C	at 16.6°C	at 0°C	at 16.6°C	
iodine	*0.0480	*0.0628	0.02064	0.02741	1.435	1.430	0.042

*Taken from published data.¹¹

According to Hildebrand¹² whenever a compound formation (or its equivalent) occurs between the components, a negative deviation from Raoult's law is produced and the solubility of such a substance which is capable of specific interaction with the solvent molecule, increases than the calculated solubility in accordance of equation (1) given below.

$$\log \frac{a_2}{x_2} = \frac{V_2 (\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 \varphi_1^*}{4.575 T} \quad (1)$$

where a_2 and x_2 are the ideal and calculated solubilities at the temperature, T , V_2 is the molar volume of the solute, φ_1^* is the volume fraction of the solvent, and δ_1 and δ_2 are the solubility parameters of the respective components. The ideal solubility a_2 at the temperature is given by the relation

$$\log \frac{1}{a_2} = \frac{H_f (T_m - T)}{4.575 T_m T} \quad (2)$$

where H_f is the heat of fusion of the solid and T_m is the melting temperature. The critical data, required in above equations (1) and (2) together with ideal solubility obtained from (13) is recorded in table II. In table III are recorded the measured and calculated solubility, formation constants of the complex and heats of formation as obtained from solubility measurements.

It is seen from table III that the measured solubilities are greater than the calculated solubilities. Weak charge transfer complexes are therefore formed because of specific interaction. The difference between the measured and calculated solubility is the amount which has gone into combination.

12. J. H. Hildebrand and R. L. Scott, Solubility of Non-Electrolytes, 3rd edition (1950).

13. A. Stedel, Solubility of Non-Electrolytes (1940).

* φ_1^* = volume fraction of the solvent, which was approximately estimated.

If two unlike molecules, X and Y, interact

$$\text{then} \quad K = N_z / (N_x - N_z) (N_y - N_z) \quad (4)$$

where N_z , $(N_x - N_z)$, and $(N_y - N_z)$ are the equilibrium concentrations in mole fraction units of Z, X and Y respectively. The measured solubility is N_x and $(1 - N_x)$ is N_y , and the difference between the measured and the calculated solubility is the amount of N_z .

The calculated values of formation constants and the heats of formation are recorded in table III. These results indicate that weak complexes are formed between the molecules of nitrobenzene and various hydrocarbons because of specific interaction. The values recorded for benzene-iodine and ether-iodine are in agreement with the previously obtained values using spectrophotometric methods⁴.

The views of Mulliken¹⁴ and Hildebrand¹⁵ and their coworkers, attributing a predominant role to the non-specific forces operative in solutions, are contradicted by these results.

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